

The Impact of ICT on Learning

Abdulkadir KIRMIZI
Yeditepe University Oct 2005
ISTANBUL

Presenter

■ Abdulkadir Kırmızı

◆ Academic Career

- Yeditepe University - PhD. in Management and Organization - Expected
- Marmara University - Master in Theory of Economy - 1998
- Boğaziçi University - Computer Engineering - 1994

◆ Working Career

- Dışbank - Application Development Director - (2004-Present)
- Dışbank - IT Audit Manager - (1999-2004)
- Akbank - Software Engineer - (1994-1998)

Learning alphabet has changed !

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3

Nothing can stop technology !

4

Agenda

- Defining Concepts (ICT, Learning)
- Learning Theories
- Learning Environments
- Impact of ICT on Learning and Teaching
 - ◆ On Learning
 - ◆ On Curriculum
 - ◆ On Learning Environment
 - ◆ On Pedagogy and Teaching
 - ◆ On Libraries
- Impact of ICT - Examples
- Implications

5

What is ICT ?

more devices...

more complexity...

Source: Gates, 2004

6

Learning

7

Learning

- Psychological - A change in behavior (Smith, 1993)
- Educational - Acquire skills (Atkin, 1994)
- Beyond Individual - "Learning Organizations" (Senge, 1992)
- "Lifelong learning"

8

Learning Theories

9

Learning Theories

- Cognitive - Understand and internalize
- Social - social environment hinders or develops (Vygotsky, 1962)
- Constructivist - Learner is active (Dewey, 1966; Bredo, 1994)
- Experiential - Learning is composed of meaningful experiences

10

Learning Environments

Source: Newhouse, 2002

11

Constructivist Learning Environment

- ▶ Learner is active participant - *learner centered*
- ▶ Focus is on what and why - *knowledge centered*
- ▶ Ongoing assessments are necessary - *assessment centered*
- ▶ Learning is affected by its context - *community centered*

Source: US Committee on Developments in the Science of Learning, 2000

12

Constructivist Learning Environment

Source: Jonassen, 2005

13

Relationship Map of Learning Process

Source: Newhouse, 2002

14

Impact on Learning

- No direct link between ICT and learning (Salomon, 1994)
- No relation between the average amount of ICT and its effectiveness in raising standards (Becta, 2002 - ImpaCT2 Study UK) - Type of use is important !
- Indirectly positive impact ? Yes !
 - ◆ Schacter(1999)
 - ◆ Mann et al. (1999)
 - ◆ Becta(2002)

15

Impact on Curriculum

- Two way relationship (Newhouse, 2002)
- The effectiveness of using ICT is a function of curriculum content and instructional strategy (Cradler and Bridgfort, 2002)
- The use of ICT impacts on both "what" and "how" of the curriculum (Riel, 1998)
- The degree varies according to disciplines

16

Impact on Learning Environment

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"There aren't any icons to click. It's a chalk board."

17

Impact on Learning Environment

- Allows to investigate more thoroughly the real world
- Able to readily access the information outside the classroom
- Active learning and authentic assessment
- Engage students by motivation and challenge
- Provide tools to increase student productivity
- Overcome physical disabilities !

18

Impact on Learning Environment

- "There will be no schools without internet connection until the end of 2006" R.T. Erdoğan - Turkey Prime Minister - 26/09/2005

19

Impact on Learning Environment

- Internet Usage (Internetworldstats.com)

Country	Internet Usage (2005)	Use Growth (2000-2005)
Sweden	73 %	64 %
Germany	57 %	96 %
Greece	34 %	280 %
Hungary	30 %	326 %
Turkey	13 %	411 %

20

Impact on Pedagogy and Teaching

■ Teachers

- ◆ Feel reduced influence
- ◆ Increased interest in teaching and experimentation
- ◆ Require more collaboration and communication with teachers, parents and students
- ◆ Require more planning and energy
- ◆ Require development of skills of ICT
- ◆ Lead to greater productivity

21

Impact on Pedagogy and Teaching

■ Pedagogy

- ◆ More learner centered
- ◆ More cooperative and collaborative
- ◆ More active learning
- ◆ Based on greater access to information and sources of information

22

Impact on Libraries

- Digital information, No need for physical access
- Digital information can be cut/copied and pasted from one document into another
- Digital information may be free or cheaper than print equivalents
- Digital information often modifies librarians' roles in various ways

23

Source : UNESCO-PROAP 1999

Impact on Librarians

- Need ICT knowledge, skill
- Continous learning of changing ICT
- Role of librarian :
 - ◆ Creators
 - ◆ Collector
 - ◆ Communicator
 - ◆ Consolidator
- From passive "gatekeeper" to active "facilitator"

24

Information Age Library

- Networked
 - Stocked with a core collection that is multimedia
 - Have access to global information
 - Digital
 - Virtual
-
- From "Library" to "Knowledge Center" or "Knowledge Node"

25

Impact of ICT - at Home

- Baran's chess lessons

26

Impact of ICT - at Work

■ Dışbank e-learning platform - Ideal Kampüs

27

Impact of ICT - at Unv

■ Knowledge Management in Yeditepe University MBA Program

28

Implications

- Have a vision for the use of technology
- Suit technology to your goals
- Combine instructive and constructive way in teaching
- Use technology where appropriate
- Nothing can replace face-to-face training/education requirement
- Technology supports learning, not replacing teachers

29

Conclusion

ICT helps !

30